

Synthesis of Hexahydro- α -Coumaranone.

BY RANAJIT GHOSH.

Hexahydro- α -coumaranone, previously obtained by Wallach (*Annalen*, 1907, **353**, 292), Coffey (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, **42**, 387) and also by Braun and Munch (*Annalen*, 1928, **465**, 52), has now been prepared in quantity by a different method, with a view to study Friedel-Crafts' reaction on bicyclic- γ -lactones with aromatic hydrocarbons, phenols, phenol-ethers, etc. (*cf.* Eijkmann, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1904, **I**, 1416 ; 1905, **I**, 1388 ; 1907, **II**, 2045) and to convert the resulting products to phenanthrene derivatives.

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate obtained by the method of Kotz (*Annalen*, 1906, **350**, 210) was converted to diethyl cyclohexanone-2-acetate-2-carboxylate (I) by its interaction with ethyl chloroacetate in presence of sodium. cycloHexanone-2-acetic acid (II), obtained by hydrolysis of the ester, was reduced by means of sodium amalgam and then heated with dilute sulphuric acid yielding the lactone hexahydro- α -coumaranone (III) in good yield.

In order to compare the properties of the above lactone with those of the lactone obtained by Wallach's method (*loc. cit.*) and also by the method of Braun and Munch (*loc. cit.*), $\Delta^{1:2}$ -cyclohexene-acetic acid was converted into the lactone in the presence of sulphuric acid according to the method of Linstead and Meade (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 942) and the lactone is identical with the hexahydro- α -coumaranone described in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxy-2-acetate.—Finely divided metallic sodium (11.5 g.) in dry benzene (300 c.c.) was slowly treated with ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (87 g.) and kept overnight. Ethyl chloroacetate (63 g.) was then added and the mixture refluxed on the water-bath for 5 hours. It was then cooled, washed with water, dried over CaCl_2 and the benzene removed and the residual oil was distilled at 161-162°/5 mm., yield 60 g. [Found: C, 60.56; H, 7.9; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 256.3. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 60.93; H, 7.81 per cent. M. W., 256). The above reaction of cyclohexanone-2-carboxylic ester with chloroacetic ester and sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution results in poor yield.

cycloHexanone-2-acetic acid was prepared by heating the foregoing ester (50 g.) with concentrated hydrochloric acid (d 1.19, 100 c. c.) and water (50 c. c.) for 7 hours. The clear aqueous solution was decanted off and water removed under reduced pressure and the thick reddish brown liquid was distilled at 168-173°/7 mm. (redistilled at 169°-170°/7 mm.), yield 20 g. (Found: C, 61.45; H, 7.75; Equiv., 155.2. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 61.55; H, 7.69 per cent. Equiv., 156).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in aqueous solution and crystallised from ethyl alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 199-200°. (Found: C, 50.57; H, 7.1; N, 19.58. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires C, 50.7; H, 7.04; N, 19.7 per cent). The semicarbazone is acidic and gives effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution.

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-acetate.—The foregoing keto acid (20 g.) was dissolved in alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (3 g. of Na in 200 c. c. of absolute alcohol) and refluxed for 9 hours with ethyl bromide (35 g.). It was then cooled, treated with water and extracted with ether, dried over calcium chloride, the ether removed and the residue distilled at 128-135°/10 mm. (redistilled at 130°/10 mm.),

yield 15 g. [Found: C, 65.18; H, 8.72; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 187. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.21; H, 8.69 per cent. M. W., 184]. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethyl alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 196°. (Found: N, 17.48. $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17.43 per cent).

Hexahydro- α -coumaranone.—(a) *cyclo*Hexanone-2-acetic acid (20 g.) was reduced with sodium amalgam (30%, 400 g.) and a stream of carbon dioxide was bubbled through it. After the sodium amalgam was exhausted, the solution was acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and boiled for some time. The liquid was then cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether removed and the residue distilled at 135°-142°/15 mm. (redistilled at 137°/15 mm. or at 130°/10 mm.; cf. Coffey, 138-139°/15 mm; Braun and Munch, 129-130°/13 mm.); yield 10 g. [Found: C, 68.51; H, 8.60; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene) 144. $C_8H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57 per cent. M. W., 140). The oil is very sparingly soluble in water, does not give effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution. It dissolves in hot caustic soda solution. It has also a characteristic sweet odour.

(b) $\Delta^{1:2}$ -*cyclo*Hexene-acetic acid (prepared by Wallach's method, *loc. cit.*) was treated with sulphuric acid and kept at 90° for 30 minutes. It was then cooled and poured into crushed ice, the oil extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and after removal of ether, distilled at 135-138°/15 mm. as a colourless oil. [Found: C, 68.48; H, 8.62; M. W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 146. $C_8H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57 per cent. M. W., 140). Its properties are the same as those described under the lactone obtained by the the method (a).

In conclusion I wish to express my sincere thanks to Sir P. C. Rây for the kind interest he took during the investigation and also for placing the resources of his laboratory at my disposal.